

Postharvest coatings from mushroom by-products

Introduction

The MicoCoating initiative aims to apply bioactive compounds of natural origin, via mushrooms that produce functional compounds, in edible coatings for the food market. Currently, the increase in shelf life, via the organic market, through the significant reduction of preservatives in the context of the clean label market, and even the consumer demand for healthier foods, is one of the main challenges of the food industry. The use of edible films and coatings has proven to be a technology with great potential to achieve longer shelf lives, while ensuring food safety and quality attributes. Market demands have led to the need to invest in alternative compounds for application in coatings that inactivate the deteriorating reactions in food while guaranteeing the quality attributes expected by the consumer.

The compounds that make up the coatings must meet certain requirements, namely having a natural origin, being renewable and edible, and should also, if possible, give the coatings bioactive and preservative properties. The search for new compounds opened new opportunities for the incorporation of natural preservatives derived from plants, animals, bacteria, algae and fungi that act as antioxidant and antimicrobial agents. Among fungi, mushrooms are generally consumed as food and it has been demonstrated, namely by the operational group, that they have the potential to be used as a source of antimicrobials and antioxidants. Thus, the bet on mushrooms of wild species (forest co-products, with no food value) and production mushrooms (using agroforestry substrates) as a source of functional compounds presents itself as a great opportunity with high added value. Taking into account the most recent developments, the main objective of this initiative was the application of bioactive compounds of natural origin, via mushrooms that produce functional compounds, in edible coatings for the food market, to increase shelf life. Operations for sorting mushrooms at the industrial level usually generate large amounts of bio-residues not conforming to strict morphological criteria for commercial purposes, even though their biological content is not compromised. In this context, the present work aimed at evaluating the potential for reutilizing industrially discarded *Agaricus blazei* Murill (ABM).

Methodology and results

Thus, the content of essential nutrients and the chemical composition were determined, and MTT and LDH assays were used to evaluate the viability and cell death of Caco-2 and HT29 cell lines of an ethanolic extract prepared from ABM (preliminary safety tests for nutraceutical applications). The extract was incorporated into a semi-solid base cosmetic cream and cell viability effects of the extract, and of the final cream formulation, on a keratinocyte cell line (HaCaT) were studied (preliminary safety tests for cosmeceutical applications). Essential nutrients, such as proteins and carbohydrates, and a low-fat content were determined for ABM. Twenty-two fatty acids were detected, with polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) (~53%) being the most abundant fraction. The cell viabilities of Caco-2 and HT29 cells were maintained up to 100 µg mL⁻¹. After incorporation into the base cream, a formulation with a pale-yellow colour and favourable pH was obtained. The cell viability of HaCaT cells in the presence of the extract and the final cream formulation was maintained in a concentration dependent manner, which indicates the safety of this extract for cosmeceutical applications. The results suggest that ABM residues can be used as an inexpensive and sustainable source of nutraceutical and cosmeceutical ingredients.

Lessons learned

Despite the discovery of many medicinal mushrooms and the identification of their bioactive polysaccharides, there are only a handful of functional food products where these polysaccharides are used. This is probably because there are several concerns regarding the application of these important molecules in final food products, such as the diversity of the biopolymers, the unstable quantity, quality and availability of these mushroom polysaccharides, the impact of the purification process and food processing on the bioactivity of the biopolymers and their production costs. Additionally, safety issues and regulation are essential for considering the marketing of functional food products. An example of this point is the limited practical applications of ergosterol and vitamin D₂ from mushroom by-products, which requires further work to achieve food and pharmaceutical industries applications.

The majority of the studies concerning the mushrooms potential bioactivity are conducted with samples of fruiting bodies. Nevertheless, the by-products generated from mushroom production also represent a good source of valuable compounds. These bioactive compounds could originate from solid substrate fermentation (caps and stipes from fruiting bodies, mycelium from SMS and SMS) or from submerged liquid fermentation (fermentation broth and surplus mycelium).

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Further information

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